

Assessing Household Carbon Footprints: A Study in Khulna's Urban and Rural Settings

Arraf Hossin^{1*}, Jobaer Monjur² and Atikur Rahman Rana³

1. Student, Department of Urban and Regional Planning, Khulna University of Engineering & Technology, Khulna-9203, Bangladesh.
E-mail: hossinarrafkuet19@gmail.com
2. Student, Department of Urban and Regional Planning, Khulna University of Engineering & Technology, Khulna-9203, Bangladesh.
E-mail: jobaermonjur@gmail.com
3. Student, Department of Civil Engineering, Khulna University of Engineering & Technology, Khulna-9203, Bangladesh.
E-mail: atikur.bh88@gmail.com

- *Corresponding author: Arraf Hossin¹

Abstract: Carbon footprint assessment of a household measures the total amount of greenhouse gases (GHG) emitted by a household's activities and helps to understand the contribution of an individual household to climate change. In this study, the individual carbon footprints of households from urban and adjacent rural areas of Khulna city have been estimated. Data was collected on three dimensions which are household, transport and lifestyle through a household level survey from multiple residential locations of Khulna city corporation (KCC) area and *Jogipole*, *Senhati* and *Aichgati* unions. These three dimensions covered data on consumption of goods and services like electricity, transport, diet of individuals etc resulting in GHG emissions. A total of 120 households were surveyed in which 70 were from urban population of KCC area and 50 from adjacent rural population of the above mentioned three unions. The UN carbon footprint calculator was used to calculate the household level carbon footprints. This calculator was developed as part of the United Nations broader initiatives to track and reduce greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions among individuals and organizations and uses country-specific reference values in carbon footprint calculation. The average annual per household carbon footprint was estimated to be 13.50 tonnes CO_{2e} in the urban area and 12.75 tonnes CO_{2e} in the adjacent rural areas. Again, the average annual per capita carbon footprint was estimated to be 3.58 tonnes CO_{2e} in the urban area and 2.57 tonnes CO_{2e} in the adjacent rural areas. This study has investigated the activity-wise carbon footprint assessment of Khulna in urban and rural settings.

Keywords: GHG; Carbon footprint; UNFCCC; Khulna; Urban; Rural.

1. Introduction

In this era of urbanization cities are becoming more congested and centers for human activities which acting as the major contributors to climate change. Climate change, a pressing global challenge, is primarily driven by anthropogenic greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions. Seven types of greenhouse gases are covered by the Kyoto Protocol and the Paris Agreement which are: Carbon dioxide (CO₂), Methane (CH₄), Nitrous oxide (N₂O), Hydrofluorocarbons, Perfluorocarbons, Sulphur hexafluoride, Nitrogen trifluoride (Climate Change: The Greenhouse Gases Causing Global Warming, 2023). Among these, carbon dioxide is a significant contributor and may be labelled as the primary driver of global climate change.

The total global CO₂ emissions from fossil fuels and land use change till 2022 was 41.46 billion tonnes and in Bangladesh it was 110.90 million tonnes (Ritchie & Roser, 2024). The annual per capita CO₂ emission of Bangladesh is 0.6 tonnes per person which is significantly lower than the global per capita emission of 4.7 tonnes per year (Ritchie & Roser, 2022). Despite of just 0.4% contribution to global GHG emissions, Bangladesh's large population and fast economic growth, GHG emissions will increase substantially (Urgent Climate Action Crucial for Bangladesh to Sustain Strong Growth, 2022). So, “carbon footprint” has become mainstream as interest grows in calculating non-financial impacts of government, business, and individual activities (J. S. Mulrow et al., 2017).

Understanding and mitigating individual carbon footprint can be a step forward to reducing the CO₂ emissions. Since households are the unit of human settlements like cities, neighbourhoods etc, it is vital to measure the carbon footprints of households. Again, in Bangladesh, a large population reside in rural areas. Although the rural areas are less developed than the urban areas, the rural population are also advancing with modernity as well as their CO₂ emissions. Developed transport network with cities, availability of natural gas and electricity and proximity to city areas influence the CO₂ emissions of rural people. So, it is crucial to measure the household carbon footprints for developing effective community-based mitigation strategies and fostering sustainable practices.

This study was guided by the following objectives,

1. Assessing the carbon footprint of households in urban and rural areas.
2. Understanding the variation in carbon footprints in urban and rural areas.

2. Methodology

2.1 Study Area

The present study was conducted in Khulna, the third largest city of Bangladesh and in its adjacent rural areas. The city of Khulna is located at 22°49'N Latitude & 89°33'E Longitude. The urban area was considered as the KCC ward boundary which consists of 31 wards and the rural area selected was the surrounding three unions- *Aichgati*, *Senhati* and *Jogipole*.

2.2 Data Collection

In this study, a questionnaire was prepared including the details of household, transport and lifestyle questions and data was gathered on household level via a questionnaire survey. As the urban area few residential locations from different wards of Khulna city corporation were surveyed. A total of 70 households were surveyed from the urban population. As the rural area three adjacent unions which are near KCC ward boundary were surveyed. These are *Aichgati* union (near ward 15), *Senhati* union (near ward 05) and *Jogipole* union (near ward 01). A total of 50 households were surveyed from the rural population.

To estimate the carbon footprint of households, data was gathered in following three dimensions,

- Household: In this part, data was gathered on household information such as family size, type of housing, size of household (m²), electricity consumption per month (KWh), source of heating etc.
- Transport: In this part, data was gathered on how all the family members get around. Questions included average hours per week travelled by all family members using train, intercity bus, city bus, bicycle/walk etc, if the family use a car or motorcycle, private flights per year on variety of ranges etc.
- Lifestyle: This part included questions on household's preferred diet (mostly meat, sometimes meat, rarely meat/fish mostly, vegetarian), if the members used mostly local made products and bought products from environmentally responsible companies, frequency of eating out in a week by the all-family members, how the family handled their wastes (if they recycle or compost food, paper, tin cans, plastic, glass etc).

2.3 Carbon Footprint Calculation

To calculate household's annual carbon footprint United Nations carbon footprint calculator was used. This calculator is a part of United Nations carbon offset platform under the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC), a web-based tool that allows to calculate household carbon footprint based on household, transport and lifestyle activities. This calculator is also known as 'Climate neutral' can be accessed from this link address: <http://climateneutralnow.org/Pages/footprintcalculator.aspx>(J. Mulrow et al., 2019). This calculator estimates household emissions based on the latest country specific data and all data is obtained from external and reliable sources (EDGAR, EPA, Climate Watch, ICAO and other organizations) and it recalculates the greenhouse gas emissions associated with different activities in CO₂ equivalent and assigns country-specific reference values to activities (UN Carbon Footprint Calculator.). The final output gives the total annual carbon footprint of a household and shows activity-wise contribution to the total footprint. The individual per capita annual values for carbon footprint were also calculated by dividing the total household carbon footprint with number of people in the household.

2.4 Limitations

Since this study was conducted based on household surveys and interviews from people, the data gathered were informed by the people. So, it may lead to some personal errors. Again, exact values of travel time of family members per week via different transport modes were hard to obtain.

3. Results

3.1 Urban Area

- The annual average per household carbon footprint was calculated 13.50 tonnes and annual average per capita carbon footprint was calculated 3.58 tonnes. Average family size was found to be around 4 persons per family who reside in households of 126.4 m² on average. The average electricity consumption per month per household was found around 238.16 KWh.

Figure 1. Family size wise total and average carbon footprint & total and average electricity consumption of Khulna city area.

3.2 Rural Area

- The annual average per household carbon footprint was calculated 12.75 tonnes and annual average per capita carbon footprint was calculated 2.57 tonnes. Average family size in adjacent rural areas of Khulna city was found to be around 5 persons per family who reside in households of 101.02 m² on average. The average electricity consumption per month per household was found around 74.29 KWh.

Figure 2. Family size wise total and average carbon footprint & total and average electricity consumption of adjacent rural areas.

3.3 Urban-Rural Comparison Table

The following table shows the composition of different family sizes from urban and rural area in this study, the activity-wise contribution to household carbon footprint as estimated from the UN carbon footprint calculator and food habit of urban and rural population of Khulna.

Category	Urban Area (%)	Rural Area (%)
Family Size Composition		
2-Members Family	8.60%	2.00%

3-Members Family	24.30%	8.00%
4-Members Family	45.70%	28.00%
5-Members Family	18.60%	30.00%
6-Members Family	-	16.00%
7-Members Family	2.90%	14.00%
8-Members Family	-	2.00%
Activity-wise Carbon Footprint (CF) Contribution		
Lifestyle	71.10%	73.80%
Transport (Land)	10.30%	8.30%
Transport (Air)	3.10%	-
Household Activities	15.50%	17.90%
Household Food Habits		
Mostly Meat	7.10%	6.00%
Mostly Fish	47.10%	8.00%
Meat in Some Meals	45.70%	84.00%
Vegetarian	-	2.00%

Table 1. Comparison of the results of urban and rural area based on family size composition, activity-wise CF contribution & household food habits.

4. Conclusion

- From this study we can see that the annual average carbon footprint of households from Khulna city area (13.50 tonnes/year) is slightly higher than that of adjacent rural areas (12.75 tonnes/year) near Khulna city. The main contributor turns out to be the higher consumption of electricity in urban areas (238.16 KWh/month) than rural areas (74.29 KWh/month). However, the factors that have kept rural carbon footprints of households close to urban carbon footprints are that the number of family members is higher in rural areas than urban areas, rural people live in a close proximity to urban area so they depend on urban locations for work, education and other activities which necessitates in daily vehicular movement in and out the city area on a regular basis. For this similar reason, per capita carbon footprints of urban and rural population are also close which are 3.58 tonnes/year (urban) and 2.57 tonnes/year respectively. This study shows that how location of households can influence the carbon footprints of both households and individuals and how lifestyle plays a vital role in contributing to carbon footprints. This study can play an important role in future calculations and comparisons of rural-urban climate footprints and assist forming effective climate mitigation and adaptation strategies for both rural and urban environments.

Acknowledgment

We express our deepest appreciation to both the residents of Khulna city and rural areas for their patience, cooperation, and provision of the most accurate data possible for this study.

References

1. Climate change: the greenhouse gases causing global warming. (2023, March 23). European Parliament. <https://www.europarl.europa.eu/topics/en/article/20230316STO77629/climate-change-the-greenhouse-gases-causing-global-warming>
2. Mulrow, J., Machaj, K., Deanes, J., & Derrible, S. (2019). The state of carbon footprint calculators: An evaluation of calculator design and user interaction features. *Sustainable Production and Consumption*, 18, 33–40. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.spc.2018.12.001>
3. Mulrow, J. S., Derrible, S., Ashton, W. S., & Chopra, S. S. (2017). Industrial Symbiosis at the Facility Scale. *Journal of Industrial Ecology*, 21(3), 559–571. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jiec.12592>
4. Ritchie, H., & Roser, M. (2022). Bangladesh: CO2 Country Profile. *Our World in Data*. <https://ourworldindata.org/co2/country/bangladesh#citation>
5. Ritchie, H., & Roser, M. (2024, January). CO2 emissions. *Our World in Data*. <https://ourworldindata.org/co2-emissions#article-citation>
6. UN carbon footprint calculator. (n.d.). United Nations Carbon Offset Platform. Retrieved July 27, 2024, from <https://offset.climateneutralnow.org/howtooffset>
7. Urgent Climate Action Crucial for Bangladesh to Sustain Strong Growth. (2022, October 31). World Bank Group. [https://www.worldbank.org/en/news/press-release/2022/10/31/urgent-climate-action-crucial-for-bangladesh-to-sustain-strong-growth#:~:text=At%20just%200.4%20percent%2C%20Bangladesh's,GHG\)%20emissions%20is%20not%20significant](https://www.worldbank.org/en/news/press-release/2022/10/31/urgent-climate-action-crucial-for-bangladesh-to-sustain-strong-growth#:~:text=At%20just%200.4%20percent%2C%20Bangladesh's,GHG)%20emissions%20is%20not%20significant)